

Beyond the binary: Third space allyship and equity in the academy

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Higher education professionals work hard to promote diversity of thought and create safe spaces for learners to contribute, but how many of us feel our workplaces do the same for ourselves and our colleagues? We argue that third space professionals possess unique strengths and opportunities to foster a more inclusive higher education work environment.

In this presentation, we made visible those third space attributes which allow us to be effective and active allies, offered practical strategies for everyday allyship, and shared some of the progress, pitfalls and possibilities of a longer-term project to establish a faculty allyship network.

Acknowledgement of Country

We stand today on the unceded lands of the Wurundjeri People of the Kulin Nations. We acknowledge their continuing connection the Land, Water and Sky Country and the fire of Knowledge they continue to hold and preserve as they have over thousands of generations. We pay our respects to their Elders, past and present and to any First Nations Peoples who are here with us today.

In working in the education space and speaking directly on matters of allyship and equity, it is critical that we recognise the ways in which Indigenous ways of Knowing have been often viewed as lesser as well as their active exclusion from Western learning institutions.

We recognise the important role of Indigenous Knowledge and ways of Knowing in all sites of learning and teaching and the importance of disassembling the ongoing structural barriers in place to seek true justice for Indigenous Australians.

Why this session?

We hope you will:

- ▣ Recognise the depths of your ability to influence change
- ▣ Explore some ways of taking action
- ▣ Reflect on your own space and what allyship is needed there

Some ground rules

- Be respectful towards one another
- Accommodate yourself however you need to support your participation
- Laugh at our jokes, we are funny 😄

Intention	Participants grow to appreciate their potential as active allies into the future
Desired Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the depths of your ability to influence change • Become familiar with with some ways of taking action • Reflect on your own space and what allyship is needed there
Agenda	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is allyship? 2. Why are third spacers uniquely positioned for allyship? 3. Taking action: everyday steps 4. Taking action: Organising
Role	Participate in the prompts and reflect on points raised for your own practice
Rules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be respectful towards one another • Accommodate yourself however you need to support your participation • Laugh at our jokes, we are funny 😄
Time	20 minutes

What is allyship?

An **ongoing** way of **changing the world**, one person, one place, one practice at a time.

See our slides: <https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

7 ally archetypes

From Karen Catlin's *Better Allies: Everyday Action to Create Inclusive, Engaging Workplaces*

See our slides: <https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

Why is allyship needed?

The fifty million diversity wheels of the internet...

All essentially communicate the plurality of human experience but our societies decide that just a few "kinds" of human are "normal".

... etc.

See our slides: <https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

The power of intersections

“ the self can only come into being when it is in dialogic relation with others ”

Lipari, 2014, p. 130

Third spacers...

- work at the intersections
- experience exclusion
- struggle to balance plural identities
- have to fight for recognition

- have privileged access to the spaces of others
- are fluent in multiple discourses
- are building spaces to honour and support each other.

Taking action

See our slides:
<https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

Taking action
Everyday allyship

How did some of what you shared match with these?

- SPONSOR
- CHAMPION
- AMPLIFY
- ADVOCATE
- LEARN
- LISTEN
- STAND UP

See our slides:
<https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

Taking action
Organising

- Aster has been part of two allyship groups built at the same time
- Establishing psychological safety
- Creating self-sustaining collectives

Allies need allies!
You can't be an organising committee of one.

See our slides:
<https://bit.ly/48M7E93>

Close

All the pieces of treasure you've heard from us and others in the session are in the chest to the right.

Now you have to pick just one to take with you as you leave.

"What one thing will you do differently when you return to the real world?"

(for you D&D players, I promise it's not a mimic)

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